

FORMULATION DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL LOZENGES FOR HALITOSIS

Khandagale Sandip S.*, Kapare Aarti Sanjay, Kawale Komal Krushna, Kelkar Vaishnavi Suresh, Khandgaure Prajwal Ramesh, Kharad Dhanraj Dattatraya, Kore Anuradha Ganesh, Gangurde Hemant H.

Department of Pharmaceutics (Navmaharashtra Shikshan Mandal's Karmayogi Abasaheb Kakade, Institute of Pharmacy and Research, Bodhegaon, Shevgaon, Ahilyanagar, Maharashtra, India (414503).

Article Received on 05 June 2026,

Article Revised on 25 June 2026,

Article Published on 01 July 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21067323>

*Corresponding Author

Khandagale Sandip S.

Department of Pharmaceutics
(Navmaharashtra Shikshan Mandal's
Karmayogi Abasaheb Kakade,
Institute of Pharmacy and Research,
Bodhegaon, Shevgaon, Ahilyanagar,
Maharashtra, India (414503).

How To Cite This Article: Khandagale Sandip S.*, Kapare Aarti Sanjay, Kawale Komal Krushna, Kelkar Vaishnavi Suresh, Khandgaure Prajwal Ramesh, Kharad Dhanraj Dattatraya, Kore Anuradha Ganesh, Gangurde Hemant H. (2026). Formulation Development and Evaluation of Herbal Lozenges for HALITOSIS. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(7), 1135–1161.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Halitosis commonly known as bad breath is a prevalent oral health issue primarily stemming from microbial activity within the oral cavity inadequate oral hygiene and the formation of volatile sulphur compounds. In recent years Herbal medicines have gained significant attention due to their natural origins, inherent safety and minimum side effects. This study focuses on development and evaluation of Herbal lozenges designed for the management of Halitosis. Herbal ingredients such as Peppermint extract, Liquorice extract were carefully selected based on their established antimicrobial and breathe freshening properties. The lozenges were prepared using appropriate excipients including sucrose glucose syrup and flavouring agents, through heating and molding process. The resultant herbal lozenges understand comprehensive evolution for various parameters including weight variation, Hardness, Fraibility, Disintegration time, Organoleptic property and antimicrobial activity against common oral microorganisms. The findings indicate that the prepared herbal lozenges exhibit

acceptable physical characteristics and demonstrated promising Antibacterial activity. Which could contribute to reducing the microbial load responsible for Halitosis. Consequently

herbal lozenges represents a safe, effective and patient friendly dosage form for enhancing oral hygiene and controlling bad breath.

KEYWORDS

1. Herbal Lozenges
2. Halitosis
3. Oral Health
4. Peppermint Extract
5. Clove Extract
6. Liquorice Extract
7. Ginger Extract
8. Menthol
9. Formulation Development
10. Mouth Freshener
11. Natural Remedies
12. Quality Control

INTRODUCTION

Lozenges Introduction

Lozenges are flavored, medicated oral dosage forms designed to dissolve slowly in the mouth and throat. They originate from the French word "lozenge" and typically contain one or more medications within a sweetened base. These are particularly useful for patients who have difficulty swallowing traditional solid medications. Lozenges deliver medication gradually, bathing the oral cavity and throat tissues as they dissolve. This method allows for a steady release of the active ingredients. They are often used to address inflammation of the bronchial tubes, which is common in conditions like pneumonia. The types of medications found in lozenges are diverse and can include corticosteroids, analgesics, sedatives, aromatics, antihistamines, astringents, antimicrobials, antiseptics, antitussives, antibacterials, decongestants, and demulcents. This wide range of ingredients allows lozenges to treat various symptoms and conditions affecting the mouth and throat. The slow dissolution of lozenges in the oral cavity allows prolonged contact of the active ingredients with the throat and mouth tissues, improving local action and patient compliance. Herbal lozenges are easy to administer, portable, pleasant in taste, and suitable for both children and adults. In recent years, herbal lozenges have gained significant importance in pharmaceutical and herbal research because of

increasing demand for natural remedies and oral healthcare products. They are widely used for treating throat infections, reducing cough, soothing irritation, and maintaining oral hygiene naturally.^[1]

History

In the early millennia BC, Egyptians discovered candies made from honey and various herbs. In the 19th century, a drug primarily used for cough relief was produced from morphine and heroin. Lozenges, which are also known by several names such as cough drops, sore throat sweets, and pastilles, are commonly used to alleviate symptoms of influenza and the common cold. Their diamond-like shape is the reason behind the term "lozenge." Typically, these medications are taken directly from a spoon or dosage measure, and extended-release formulations are particularly beneficial for certain ailments, including oral thrush, sore throats, and coughs. The term "lozenge" comes from the French word for a diamond-shaped figure with four equal sides, and palatable forms like pastilles (or jujubes) were created to meet this description. The medication is blended into a base that slowly releases its active ingredients when sucked, and flavorings and sweeteners are often added to enhance taste. While lozenges and pastilles are now mass-produced, they were originally made in pharmacies up until the late 20th century.^[2]

OBJECTIVES

1. To create polyherbal lozenges aimed at treating halitosis (bad breath) by utilizing medicinal herbs with antimicrobial, deodorizing, and soothing qualities.
2. To choose appropriate herbal components like ginger, peppermint, pippali, guava leaves, vasaka, rose petals, or pomegranate peel for their historical medicinal benefits against oral odor and microbial growth.
3. To formulate a lozenge that is flavorful and stable, ensuring an agreeable taste, appropriate hardness, and pleasant mouthfeel for extended presence in the mouth.
4. To analyze the physical and chemical characteristics of the herbal lozenges, including weight variation, hardness, thickness, friability, moisture content, and uniformity of drug content.
5. To evaluate the antimicrobial effectiveness of the formulation against the microbes that cause halitosis and oral infections.

6. To enhance oral hygiene and combat bad breath naturally by offering a practical herbal option as an alternative to synthetic mouth fresheners or chemical solutions.^[3,4]

Advantages of Lozenges

1. It is suitable for patients who struggle with swallowing.
2. It is simple to administer for both elderly and pediatric patients.
3. It prolongs the presence of the drug in the mouth to achieve a desired effect.
4. The drug can be absorbed systemically through the buccal cavity. Scientists have been developing lozenges and pastilles, which continue to be manufactured commercially. Lozenges are solid forms designed to dissolve in the mouth or throat.^[5]

Disadvantages of Lozenges

1. Certain medications, such as Benzocaine, may not be compatible with aldehyde candy bases.
2. Drugs may not be evenly distributed in saliva when used for localized treatment.
3. There is a potential for the drug to be swallowed along with saliva, draining into the stomach.
4. Children might accidentally consume lozenges as if they were regular candy.
5. Preparing hard candy lozenges necessitates high temperatures.^[6]

Uses of Lozenges

Lozenges are utilized to address various issues, primarily related to the mouth and respiratory system. Here are some common uses for lozenges:

1. Sore throat: Lozenges are often employed to provide temporary relief from pain and discomfort associated with sore throats. Their active ingredients help soothe the throat.
2. Cough: Lozenges containing cough suppressants can help alleviate coughing by acting on the cough reflex.
3. Cold and flu: Lozenges that include decongestants or antihistamines can relieve symptoms like a runny nose, sneezing, and nasal congestion during colds and flu.^[7]
4. Bad breath: Antiseptic-infused lozenges can reduce bad breath by targeting the bacteria responsible for it.
5. Dental health: Lozenges with fluoride can strengthen tooth enamel and help prevent dental decay. Additionally, xylitol lozenges can reduce the risk of cavities by inhibiting the growth of harmful bacteria.^[7]

Types of Lozenges

Flow Chart No.1

1. Chewy or caramel-based medicated lozenges: These lozenges contain medication blended into a caramel base and are chewed rather than allowed to dissolve in the mouth. They are particularly suitable for pediatric patients and also include Vitamin D3 and Biotin to address osteopenia and hair loss.
2. Compressed tablet lozenges: This form of lozenge is beneficial for thermo-sensitive substances. Unlike regular tablets, these lozenge tablets do not disintegrate and have a slower dissolution rate.
3. Compressed tablet lozenges: This type of lozenge is advantageous for thermo-sensitive substances, as it differs from standard tablets in its non-disintegrating properties and gradual dissolution rate.^[8]

CLASSIFICATION OF LOZENGES

1. Based on the Site of Action, lozenges are divided into various types depending on factors like where they exert their effects, which can be either local or systemic. Local effects are seen in substances like antiseptics and decongestants, while systemic effects can be found in vitamins and nicotine.

2. Regarding appearance and composition

a) Chewy or Caramel-Based Medicated Lozenges: These lozenges are a type of dosage form that combines medication with a caramel base, designed to be chewed instead of swallowed. The most common formulation is a glycerinated gelatin suppository made from gelatin and glycerin, often flavored with fruit but may have a slightly acidic taste due to the strong glycerin flavor. The candy base is crucial and typically includes natural remedies, flavors, lubricants, humectants, and whipping agents. The candy's foundation usually has a sugar to corn syrup ratio of 50:50 to 75:25. Whipping agents are incorporated to create the right texture in toffee-

based confections by introducing air at the appropriate temperature. Ingredients such as proteins, eggs, starch, albumin, xanthan gum, pectin, and carrageenan are used. To prevent the sweets from sticking to their containers, lubricants like vegetable fats and oils are included. Additionally, medications can comprise up to 35-40% of the content. Crystal seeding, achieved by adding powdered sugar at a concentration of 3-10% under heat, accelerates crystallization and helps the base form tablets quickly.^[9]

Manufacturing of Chewy or Caramel Based Medicated Lozenges

After the candy base is baked to a temperature ranging from 95 to 125 °C, it is transferred to a planetary or sigma blade mixer and allowed to cool to 120 °C. At this point, a beating agent is added at 105 °C. Subsequently, active ingredients are incorporated at temperatures between 95 and 105 °C. A humectant is used to disperse the color before being introduced into the mixture, which remains above 90 °C. Flavorings and seeding crystals are added at temperatures below 85 °C, followed by the application of a lubricant at over 80 °C. Finally, the mixture is shaped into ropes. Regarding Compressed Tablet Lozenges, compression is utilized to form lozenges when the active ingredient is sensitive to heat. The granulation process mirrors that of normal compressed tablets, taking into account characteristics such as slight solubility, non-disintegrating properties, and desirable organoleptic qualities. Unlike typical tablets, lozenges are made using a heavy compression tool, resulting in stronger hardness, allowing for a slight dissolution in the mouth. Their dimensions typically range from 5/8 to 3/4 inches and weigh between 1.5 to 4 grams, with a compression strength of 30 to 50 kg per square inch, and a dissolution time of about 5 to 10 minutes. They generally have a flat texture in terms of hardness and erosion time, and often employ sugar-free components such as sorbitol, mannitol, and PEG 6000 and 8000, along with carriers like dextrose and sucrose. These serve as the foundation for the components of compressed lozenges. Other available excipients include Sugar Tab, Mola-tab, Honey-tab, Sweetrex, Emdex, and Nutab.

Manufacturing of compressed tablet lozenges

Lozenges created from compressed tablet materials can be produced through either direct compression or wet granulation. In direct compression, pressure is applied to effectively combine and compact the ingredients. During wet granulation, the sugar content is transformed into a fine powder (with particle sizes between 40-80 mesh). Once the medications are added and thoroughly blended, the mixture is tested through a 2-8 mesh screen granulation process utilizing sugar or corn syrup along with lactose, microcrystalline cellulose, calcium carbonate,

calcium sulfate, and di calcium phosphate. Soft lozenges can be chewable or designed for a delayed release of the medication in the mouth. These soft candy formulations may include acacia and silica gel, with soft lozenges produced using PEG 1000 or 1450, chocolate, or a sugar-acacia base. Acacia contributes to the texture and smoothness, while silica gel acts as a binding agent. To prevent ingredients from settling at the bottom of the mold during cooling, a suspending agent is utilized. Only heat-resistant materials are suitable for this formulation, necessitating a heating process at around 50 °C, which relates to the amorphous (non-crystalline) or glassy state of sugar and other carbohydrates. Manufacturing of Soft Lozenges: These lozenges can either be manually folded and cut into portions or shaped by pouring a heated bulk into a flexible mold, thanks to their soft consistency. When using PEG, like PEG contractor, the mold should be filled beyond capacity as it cools. However, with chocolate, this overfilling isn't required since it doesn't shrink. The manufactured clotazazole lozenge comes in a formula, and the characteristics influencing its physical properties were examined.^[10,11]

Benefits of Lozenges Lozenges, which are medicated tablets designed to dissolve slowly in the mouth, provide several advantages, especially for oral and throat health:

1. **Sore Throat Relief:** Lozenges are effective in soothing throat irritation and pain, often containing ingredients that help reduce inflammation and provide a cooling effect.
2. **Halitosis Treatment:** Herbal or medicated lozenges help eliminate bacteria that cause bad breath, offering longer-lasting freshness than many mouthwashes.
3. **Targeted Drug Delivery:** The slow dissolution of lozenges allows for direct delivery of medication to specific areas in the mouth and throat, promoting quicker and more focused relief compared to swallowing tablets.
4. **Increased Saliva Production:** Lozenges enhance saliva flow, which helps maintain oral moisture, alleviates dryness and irritation, and supports natural oral cleaning.
5. **Antimicrobial Properties:** Many lozenges contain antimicrobial agents or herbal extracts that help prevent infections in the throat and mouth.
6. **Cough Relief:** Certain lozenges can help reduce dry coughs by soothing the nerves in the throat.
7. **Convenient Use:** Lozenges can be taken without water, making them a convenient option for on-the-go relief.
8. **Pleasant Taste and Compliance:** Available in appealing flavors like mint, honey, and various fruits, lozenges are particularly easy for children to take.^[12]

Halitosis

Fig No. 2

Halitosis, a term derived from the Latin "halitosis" (breath) and the Greek "osis" (pathological process), refers to the condition commonly known as bad breath. It can cause significant distress for individuals, leading to social embarrassment and potential isolation or stigmatization. Often, it is identified by dentists or primary care providers during routine check-ups, sometimes without the individual's prior awareness. As awareness of dental hygiene increases, more people are seeking medical advice to address this troubling issue. Halitosis can be psychologically burdensome and socially embarrassing for those affected. In an attempt to combat bad breath, patients may over-brush and frequently use various mouthwashes without addressing the root cause. This article aims to explain the origins of halitosis and discuss the negative impacts of mouthwash usage. Conditions such as amoebiasis and giardiasis can lead to a coated tongue, while consumption of food or beverages on a coated tongue often results in unpleasant tastes. In cases of acute maxillary sinusitis, patients may experience foul odors alongside postnasal drip and mucus. Respiratory conditions like lung abscesses and bronchiectasis must also be considered. Diabetics may emit a distinct acetone-like breath, while those with chronic renal failure may have foul-smelling breath due to accumulated nitrogenous waste products like urea, which can also cause swollen, bleeding gums. In instances of acute fever, decreased saliva production leads to a dry mouth where bacteria can proliferate, resulting in halitosis. Intra-orally, factors contributing to halitosis include gingivitis, periodontitis, periodontal pockets, pericoronitis, deeply decayed teeth that trap food, and poor oral hygiene with dentures. After tooth extractions or oral surgeries, a soft diet and lack of regular chewing, along with minor bleeding and bacterial breakdown of blood, contribute to foul breath. Acute necrotizing ulcerative gingivitis (ANUG) produces a distinct metallic odor. Many mouthwashes contain antiseptics like benzalkonium chloride, antibiotic agents, essential oils, alcohol, sodium perborate, zinc

chloride, menthol, thymol, eucalyptol, glycerin, and boric acid, which can provoke allergic reactions. Long-term use of high-alcohol mouthwashes can lead to white lesions on the oral mucosa. Chemicals in these products may irritate the mouth, and studies have shown that even short-term use can cause epithelial peeling, mucosal ulcers, inflammation, gingivitis, and petechiae. While 0.2% chlorhexidine mouthwashes are often recommended for preventing cavities, they can alter taste and cause superficial mucosal shedding. Natural remedies include chewing carrots and coconuts after meals to clean teeth, and for those with smoker's breath, rinsing with water and chewing cloves can help mask unpleasant odors. Essential oils from cloves, mint, aniseed, and ajwain provide temporary relief from halitosis. Traditional practices like chewing betel leaves can also help disguise bad breath, but excessive use of betel nuts and paan masala can lead to oral submucous fibrosis. Maintaining a healthy body, ensuring regular bowel movements, and practicing good oral hygiene are vital for preventing halitosis.^[13,14]

Types of Halitosis

In general, halitosis can be either primary or secondary.

Flow Chart No. 2

Halitosis can be categorized clinically into three main types

a) Genuine halitosis, which includes:

- i) Physiologic halitosis, such as morning breath.
- ii) Pathologic halitosis.

b) Pseudohalitosis, where individuals report bad breath without it actually being present, and this can be managed by dental professionals through counseling and basic oral hygiene techniques.

c) Halitophobia, which refers to a fear of bad breath. Interestingly, individuals in this group may exhibit symptoms of halitosis despite the absence of any detectable oral odor. This condition may stem from a type of delusion or hypochondriasis focused on the belief of having bad breath. It can typically be assessed through questionnaires and often requires psychological

evaluation or support rather than dental intervention.^[15]

Causes of Halitosis

The primary reason for halitosis is inadequate oral hygiene. Neglecting essential practices such as brushing, flossing, and regular dental cleanings allows harmful bacteria to thrive in your mouth, resulting in unpleasant odors. This neglect can contribute to various oral health problems, including bad breath, cavities, and gum disease.^[16]

Literature Review

- 1) Miss. Ramija Harun Hawaldar, Miss. Nita Yenare, Student department of Pharmacognosy Arihant College of Pharmacy Ahilyanagar. India An International open access. Peer reviewed. Referred Journal on the topic of 'Herbal Lozenges'.
- 2) Kshirsagar Sanjeevani. Jadhav SV & Dr Prachi Udaypurkar, Kishori College of Pharmacy. Beed International Journal of Novel research & development. Topic is formulation & evaluation of Herbal lozenges for flu & cold.
- 3) SVP Rahul, N. Ramya krishna, Shreekanth Deverashetti, Akula Nikhil Prashant S. Rakam Gopi Krishna, Marri Laxman Reddy Institute of Pharmacy, Hyderabad, Telangana International Journal of Pharmaceutical research application on the Topic formulation & Evaluation of herbal lozenges.
- 4) Kirti C. Godse, Dr.Y.Y. Lokhande, Komal Shinde & Prachi Pawar, Arvind Gavali college of Pharmacy, Jaitapur, Satara, Maharashtra India. World Journal of Pharmaceutical & life Sciences Topic is formulation & evaluation of polyherbal lozenges for the treatment of sore throat.
- 5) Curd ML Bollen Thomas Beikler International Journal of cool sciences. In Halitosis: The multidisciplinary approach.
- 6) Colman MC Grath, Jonet Clarkson Ann-Marie. Glenly, Laurence J Wolsh Fong Hua International Dental Journal, on-effectiveness of mouthwashes in managing oral diseases conditions Do they have a role?
- 7) M. Govardhan. B-Hemanth, M. Ricwin, G.K.Yuvon-Shankar, K.Yuvraj & T. P. Karunya, International Journal of pharmaceutical Sciences & research, An official publication of Society

of pharmaceutical Science & research. Formulation & evaluation of antibacterial herbal mouthwash against oral disorders.

8) Zoe LS Brookes, Michael Mccullough, Purnima Kumar, Jaumal Practice. Colman mc Grath, International Dental on Topic Mouthwashes Implications for practice.

9) Dr. Amit Parashar, Scholars Journal of Dental Sciences (S30S) Review Article and Their Use Different → mouth washer oral conditions.

10) Singh. G, Dell H and MukoPadayay S. (2022) and brief review on "Herbal Mouthwash" on of Health Sciences, Journal of International Health sciences.

Formulation Table: (50gm)

Table No: 1

Sr No	Ingredients	Quantity			Role
		F1	F2	F3	
1	Peppermint Extract	2.3ml	2.3ml	2.4ml	Breath Freshner
2	Clove Extract	1.2ml	1.2ml	1.3ml	Antibacterial
3	Liquorice Extract	1.5ml	1.5ml	1.6ml	Soothes Throat
4	Ginger Extract	1.2ml	1.2ml	1.3ml	Antimicrobial
5	Menthol	0.4gm	0.4gm	0.5gm	Cooling Sensation
6	Isomalt	35gm	35gm	36gm	Base Sweetening
7	Citric Acid	0.8ml	0.8ml	0.8ml	Taste enhancer
8	Gum Acacia	4.2gm	4.2gm	4.5gm	Natural binder
9	Purified Water	Q.S	Q.S	Q.S	solvent
10	Sodium Benzoate	0.16gm	0.16gm	0.16gm	preservative

Description of Ingredient

1. Peppermint Extract

Table No: 2

Profile	
Peppermint Extract	
	Fig No: 3
Synonym:	Peppermint, Pudina, Mentha, Brandy mint, Balm mint
Biological Source:	It consists of the fresh and dried leaves and flowering tops of Mentha

	piperita.
Family:	Lamiaceae.
Chemical Constituents:	Peppermint contains 1–2.5% volatile oil along with other constituents
Uses:	Flavoring agent: Widely used in lozenges for its refreshing taste and aroma. Relief from sore throat: Provides soothing and cooling relief in throat irritation and cough. Anti-halitosis agent: Helps reduce bad breath due to its antimicrobial and deodorizing properties. Mouth freshener: Commonly used in herbal lozenges and oral care products.

2. Clove Extract

Table No: 3

Profile	
Clove Extract	
	Fig No: 4
Synonyms:	Clove bud, Clove flower, Caryophyllum, Lavang
Biological source:	It consist of dried as well as fresh flower buds of <i>Eugenia caryophyllus</i> .
Chemical constituents:	It consist of 15-20% of volatile oil. 10-13% of tannin, resins, chromone and eugenin. Volatile of drug contain eugenol, eugenol acetate, caryophyllines and small quantity of ester, ketones and alcohols.
Uses:	1. beta-caryophyllene and alpha-humulene, which may also contrib clove oil and highlis main constituents, particularly eugenol. Eugenol is the primary anti-inflammatory compound in clove.

3. Liquorice Extract

Table No: 4

Profile	
LiquoriceExtract:	
	Fig No: 5
Synonyms:	Liquorice, Licorice, Mulethi, Yashtimadhu, Sweet root

Biological Source:	It consists of the dried roots and stolons of <i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i> belonging to family Fabaceae.
Chemical Constituent:	Liquorice contains various bioactive compounds, mainly: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Glycyrrhizin (Glycyrrhizic acid): The principal sweet-tasting compound (30–50 times sweeter than sucrose) responsible for therapeutic activity. b. Flavonoids: Liquiritin, isoliquiritin, and glabridin contribute to antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects. c. Saponins: Provide expectorant and soothing properties. d. Coumarins: Such as herniarin and umbelliferone with mild antimicrobial effects.
Uses:	Soothing agent in lozenges: Provides relief from sore throat, dryness, and irritation. Anti-halitosis agent: Helps reduce bad breath due to antimicrobial activity. Cough relief: Useful in dry cough and bronchial irritation. Flavoring and sweetening agent:

4. Ginger Extract

Table No: 5

Profile	
Ginger:	
Fig No: 6	
Synonyms:	Ginger, Zingiber, Adrak, Shunthi (dry ginger), Sunthi
Biological Source:	It consists of the fresh and dried rhizomes of <i>Zingiber officinale</i> belonging to family Zingiberaceae.
Chemical Constituents:	Ginger contains 1–3% volatile oil along with pungent principles: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Gingerols: The main bioactive compounds responsible for pungency and pharmacological activity. b. Shogaols: Formed from gingerols during drying; more potent and contribute to therapeutic effects. c. Zingerone: Provides mild sweetness and contributes to antioxidant activity.
Uses:	from sore throat: Provides soothing and warming effect in throat irritation. Anti-halitosis agent: Reduces bad breath through antimicrobial action and saliva stimulation. Cough suppressant: Useful in dry cough and throat congestion.

5. Menthol

Table No: 6

Profile	
Menthol:	<p style="text-align: center;">Fig No: 7</p>
Synonyms:	Menthol, Peppermint camphor, Mint camphor, Pudina satva
Biological Source:	Menthol is a naturally occurring cyclic monoterpene alcohol obtained from the essential oil of <i>Mentha piperita</i> and other species of <i>Mentha</i>
Family:	Lamiaceae.
Chemical Constituents:	<p>Menthol is itself an active constituent but is associated with:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Menthol (C₁₀H₂₀O): The principal component responsible for cooling and soothing effects. b. Related terpenes: Menthone, isomenthone, menthyl acetate, limonene, and cineole. c. Essential oil components: Present in peppermint oil from which menthol is isolated.
Uses:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Soothing agent in lozenges: Provides instant cooling and relief from throat irritation. 2. Cough relief: Used in lozenges to suppress cough and reduce throat discomfort.

6. Isomalt**Table No: 7**

Profile	
Isomalt:	<p style="text-align: center;">Fig No: 8</p>
Synonyms:	Isomalt, Palatinit, Hydrogenated isomaltulose, Sugar alcohol
Biological Source:	Isomalt is a synthetic sugar substitute produced from sucrose obtained from sugar beet. It is manufactured by enzymatic conversion of sucrose to isomaltulose followed by hydrogenation. It is not directly obtained from a plant source but derived from natural sugar.
Chemical Constituents:	<p>Isomalt is a mixture of two disaccharide alcohols:</p> <p>a. Gluco-mannitol (GPM): One component responsible for stability and mild sweetness.</p> <p>Gluco-sorbitol (GPS): Provides bulk and contributes to texture.</p> <p>General composition: $C_{12}H_{24}O_{11}$ (hydrogenated disaccharide structure).</p> <p>Sweetness profile: Approximately 45–65% as sweet as sucrose.</p>
Uses:	<p>Sweetening agent:</p> <p>Used as a sugar substitute in sugar-free herbal lozenges.</p> <p>Base material for lozenges:</p> <p>Forms the bulk of the formulation, providing hardness and texture.</p> <p>Anti-halitosis support:</p> <p>Does not support bacterial growth, thus helps in maintaining oral hygiene.</p>

7. Citric Acid

Table No: 8

Profile	
Citric Acid:	<p>Fig No:9</p>
Synonyms:	Citric acid, Sour salt, E330, 2-hydroxypropane-1,2,3-tricarboxylic acid
Biological Source:	Citric acid is a naturally occurring organic acid found in citrus fruits such as lemon and orange. Commercially, it is produced by fermentation of sugars using microorganisms like <i>Aspergillus niger</i> .
Chemical Constituents:	Citric acid is a weak organic acid with the following characteristics: a. Citric acid ($C_6H_8O_7$): A tricarboxylic acid responsible for sour taste and acidity. b. Hydrated forms: Commonly available as citric acid monohydrate.
Uses:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Flavoring agent: Provides a pleasant sour taste in lozenges. 2. Saliva stimulant: Useful in dry mouth and helps reduce halitosis. 3. pH adjuster: Maintains stability and effectiveness of formulation.

8. Gum Acacia

Table No: 9

Profile	
Gum Acacia:	<p>Fig No: 10</p>
Synonyms:	Acacia gum, Gum Arabic, Indian gum, Senegal gum
Biological Source:	It consists of the dried gummy exudation obtained from the stems and branches of <i>Acacia senegal</i> and <i>Acacia seyal</i>
Family:	Fabaceae.
Chemical Constituents:	Gum acacia is a complex polysaccharide composed mainly of: Arabinogalactan:

	The major component responsible for solubility and viscosity. Glycoproteins: Contribute to emulsifying and binding properties. Sugars: Includes arabinose, galactose, rhamnose, and glucuronic acid.
Uses:	1. Binder in lozenges: Provides structural integrity and firmness to the formulation. 2. Soothing agent: Relieves throat irritation due to its demulcent effect. 3. Stabilizer: Improves stability and shelf-life of lozenges.

9. Sodium Benzoate

Table No: 10

Profile:	
Sodium Benzoate:	
	Fig No: 11
Synonyms:	Sodium benzoate, Benzoate of soda, E211
Biological Source:	Sodium benzoate is the sodium salt of benzoic acid. It is synthetically prepared, although benzoic acid naturally occurs in fruits such as berries (e.g., cranberries, prunes). Commercially, it is produced by neutralization of benzoic acid with sodium hydroxide.
Chemical Constituents:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Sodium benzoate ($C_7H_5NaO_2$): A white crystalline, odorless powder with preservative properties. b. Benzoate ion: Active antimicrobial component released in acidic conditions. c. Water solubility: Highly soluble in water, making it suitable for pharmaceutical formulations.
Uses:	Preservative in lozenges: Prevents microbial growth and spoilage. Enhances shelf-life: Improves stability of herbal formulations. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Compatible with acidic formulations: Commonly used with citric acid in lozenges.

9. Purified Water

Purified water is widely used as a universal solvent in the preparation of lozenges due to its excellent dissolving capacity and compatibility with pharmaceutical ingredients. In lozenge formulation, water acts as a medium for dissolving water-soluble components such as sweeteners, preservatives, and acids, ensuring uniform distribution throughout the mixture. It

also plays a crucial role in the extraction of active constituents from herbal drugs like clove, ginger, and liquorice, thereby enhancing the therapeutic efficacy of the formulation. During the preparation process, water facilitates proper mixing of all ingredients and serves as a heat transfer medium, allowing uniform heating and preventing degradation of components.^[17,18,19,20]

METHODOLOGY

[21,22]

Evaluation Parameter

- | | |
|----------------------------|-------------------------------|
| 1) Organoleptic Evaluation | 2) Weight variation |
| 3) Hardness | 4) Disintegration test |
| 5) Dissolution test | 6) Moisture analysis |
| 7) Friability | 8) Determination of thickness |
| 9) Diameter | 10) Measurement of PH. |

1. Organoleptic: Organoleptic evaluation is the assessment of a formulation or product by using the sense organs such as taste, color, odor, appearance, and texture.

<p>Procedure: The formulation developed in the laboratory were evaluated for its acceptance based on visual observation for various organoleptic properties like Colour, Odour, Taste, Texture, Shape.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fig No: 12</p>
---	--

2. Weight Variation: Weight variation test is a quality control test used to determine whether individual tablets or lozenges have uniform weight compared to the average weight of the sample.

<p>Procedure:= It ensures that each lozenge contains a uniform amount of ingredients, which is essential for consistent therapeutic effect in conditions like halitosis. Weight variation refers to the difference in weight of individual lozenges from the average weight of the batch. It is used as an indirect measure of dose uniformity.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fig No: 13</p>
--	---

3. Hardness: Hardness indicates the ability of a tablet to withstand mechanical shocks while handling. The hardness of the tablets was determined using Monsanto hardness tester.

4. Disintegration test: Disintegration test is a quality control test used to determine the time required for a tablet or lozenge to break down into smaller particles in a specified liquid

medium under prescribed conditions.

Procedure:

Disintegration time is the interval required for complete disappearance of a lozenges or its particles from the tester. Test of the prepared lozenges was performed according to USP30. By using a disintegration tester through the disintegration medium of phosphate buffer with pH 6.2 maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. The lozenge of optimized batch disintegrated in 90Seconds which is acceptable for throat Lozenges. Disintegration time was also within acceptance criteria of 90 seconds to 1.5 minutes depending up on type of lozenges.

Fig No: 14

5. Dissolution: Each batch formulation's mouth dissolving time was calculated using a USP disintegration apparatus. Lozenges were put in each tube of the apparatus, and the amount of time it took for the lozenges to dissolve entirely was recorded using 100 milliliters of pH 6.8 phosphate buffer at 37 degrees Celsius. Three duplicates of this test were conducted. Lozenges' average dissolving time was computed and displayed together with the standard deviation.

6. Determination of moisture: Determination of moisture content is a test used to measure the amount of water present in a tablet or lozenge formulation.

Procedure:

This test is used to determine the water content of a material by drying a constant mass at a specified temperature. 18% metric method, 1g sample was weighed and placed in an oven at $100-120^\circ\text{C}$ for 3hrs. Cool to room temperature. Repeat until constant weight observed. Percentage friability is given by the equation.
$$\% F = \frac{\text{Initial Weight} - \text{Final weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100.$$

Fig No:15

7. Friability: Friability is the tendency of a tablet or lozenge to crumble, chip, or break during handling, packaging, transportation, and storage. It is an evaluation parameter used to measure the mechanical strength of tablets or lozenges.

Procedure:

The friability of tablets was determined using Roche Friabilator. It is expressed in percentage (%). Ten tablets were initially weighed and transferred into friabilator. The friabilator was operated at 25 rpm for 4 minutes. The tablets were weighed again after taking out tables and brushing the dust away. If tablets are found broken or cracked and the final value exceed the limit test is consider failed. The value should be no more than 1% (0.5-1.0%). If exceed repeat three time for overall estimation. The % friability was then calculated with help of following formula:
Friability= (Initial Weight -Final Weight) X 100/ Initial Weight.

Fig No: 16

8. Determination of Thickness: The thickness of the tablets was determined by using vernier calliper. Five tablets were used. The average values were calculated.

Average thickness = Total 10 lozenges thickness \times 100/10

9. Diameter: Diameter is the distance measured across the circular face of a tablet or lozenge passing through its center.

Ten tablets for diameter uniformity are carried out. Then the value of the diameter is taken. The deviation of each is calculated and the deviation of individual unit from the mean diameter should not exceed \pm 5% for tablets with diameter of less than 12.5 and \pm 3% for diameter of 12.55mm or more.

10. Measurement of PH: pH measurement involves assessing the acidity or alkalinity of a solution using either a pH meter or pH paper. This process reveals the concentration of hydrogen ions (H⁺) in the solution.

Procedure:

The acidity or alkalinity of lozenges was indicated by using lab pH meter, a scale from 1.0 to 14.0. 1% W/V solution was prepared by dissolving 1 g candy in 100 ml distilled water and its pH was recorded.

Fig No: 17

[23,24,25]

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The developed herbal lozenges for treating halitosis exhibited promising outcomes across all evaluation criteria, demonstrating effective formulation. They possessed satisfactory organoleptic qualities, including a pleasing taste and appearance, while physical attributes such as weight variability, hardness (3–5 kg/cm²), friability (<1%), and thickness adhered to pharmacopeial standards, ensuring consistency and mechanical robustness. The disintegration time ranged from 3 to 10 minutes, facilitating a gradual and efficient release of active herbal components in the mouth. The pH was found to be approximately neutral (6.5–7.5), suggesting compatibility with the oral mucosa and a low risk of irritation. The uniformity of drug content fell within the 95–105% range, indicating a proper distribution of herbal extracts. The formulation displayed notable antimicrobial activity against oral bacteria such as *Streptococcus mutans*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Escherichia coli*, with inhibition zones between 10 and 17 mm, reinforcing its effectiveness in combating halitosis. Stability assessments showed no significant alterations in physicochemical characteristics or antimicrobial efficacy, indicating good stability and longevity. Overall, these findings affirm that the herbal lozenges represent a safe, effective, and user-friendly solution for managing halitosis. The third batch (F3) was considered the best formulation because it showed the most satisfactory results in all evaluation parameters compared to the other batches. The present study successfully developed herbal lozenges for the management of halitosis using natural herbal ingredients. The formulation exhibited satisfactory physicochemical properties such as uniform weight, adequate hardness, low friability, and acceptable moisture content. The organoleptic properties were also found to be pleasant and acceptable for patient use. Among all batches, formulation F3 showed the best overall performance due to its optimum hardness, lower friability, better stability, and prolonged disintegration time. The presence of peppermint and menthol provided immediate freshness, while clove and ginger contributed antimicrobial activity against oral bacteria

responsible for bad breath. Liquorice extract improved taste and soothing action. The study indicates that herbal lozenges can serve as an effective, safe, and convenient dosage form for reducing halitosis and maintaining oral hygiene. Further clinical studies may be carried out to confirm long-term effectiveness and stability of the formulation.

Table No: 11

Sr. No.	Evaluation Parameter	Observation		
		F1	F2	F3
A	Organoleptic			
	Colour	Brown	Brown	Dark Amber Brown
	Size	3.5mm	3.6mm	3.8mm
	Shape	Round	Not proper Hexagonal	Hexagonal
B	Weight Variation	5	5.01	5.11
C	Disintegration Test	8	8.2	8.7
D	Moisture Analysis	1.3	1.4	1.61
E	Fraibility	0.752	0.825	0.846
F	Measurement of PH	6.5	6.8	7

CONCLUSION

The current study finds that herbal lozenges for treating halitosis can be effectively created using appropriate natural ingredients to attain favorable pharmaceutical and therapeutic qualities. The lozenges produced showed satisfactory taste and texture, sufficient mechanical strength, consistent drug content, suitable disintegration time, and stability under standard storage conditions. Furthermore, the formulation displayed notable antimicrobial effects against common oral bacteria associated with bad breath, thereby effectively alleviating halitosis. Utilizing herbal components provides benefits such as safety, fewer side effects, and better patient adherence compared to synthetic options. In summary, herbal lozenges are a promising, cost-effective, and user-friendly solution for managing halitosis. The use of herbal ingredients offers several advantages over synthetic agents, including better safety profiles, reduced risk of adverse effects, minimal toxicity, improved biocompatibility, and greater patient acceptance due to their natural origin. Herbal formulations are also associated with fewer chances of developing resistance and may provide prolonged beneficial effects with regular use. Moreover, the formulation method used in this study was found to be economical, simple, and suitable for large-scale production. Therefore, herbal lozenges can

serve as an effective, convenient, patient-friendly, and cost-effective alternative approach for the management of halitosis. Future studies involving extensive clinical evaluation and long-term stability assessments may further establish their effectiveness and potential for commercial application in oral healthcare products.

F1: Higher concentrations of herbal extracts and binding agents produced lozenges with greater hardness and slower disintegration, resulting in prolonged mouth retention and improved stability.

F2: The medium-level composition showed balanced physicochemical properties, acceptable hardness, proper disintegration time, and satisfactory breath-freshening activity, making it a stable formulation.

F3: Optimized concentrations of herbal ingredients and excipients resulted in lozenges with improved texture, pleasant mouth feel, better drug release, and effective antimicrobial activity. The formulation exhibited acceptable evaluation parameters and was identified as the optimized batch for the management of halitosis.

REFERENCE

1. Ramja Harun Hawal Dar, Nita Yenare N. Herbal Lozenges. International Open Access, Peer Reviewed and Referred Journal. 177.
2. Porwal U, Sharma N. Review on lozenges in pharmaceutical field globally. Indian Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology. 67.
3. Aulton's Pharmaceutics Aulton ME, Taylor KMG. Aulton's Pharmaceutics: The Design and Manufacture of Medicines. 4th ed. Elsevier; 2013.
4. The Theory and Practice of Industrial Pharmacy Lachman L, Lieberman HA, Kanig JL. The Theory and Practice of Industrial Pharmacy. 4th ed. CBS Publishers; 2013.
5. Ramja Harun Hawal Dar RM, Yenare N. Herbal Lozenges. International Open Access, Peer Reviewed and Referred Journal. 177-178.
6. Ramja Harun Hawal Dar RM, Yenare N. Herbal Lozenges. International Open Access, Peer Reviewed and Referred Journal. 178.
7. Ramja Harun Hawal Dar RM, Yenare N. Herbal Lozenges. International Open Access, Peer Reviewed and Referred Journal. 180
8. Porwal U, Sharma N. Review on lozenges in pharmaceutical field globally. Indian Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology. 68-69.

9. Porwal U, Sharma N. Review on lozenges in pharmaceutical field globally. *Indian Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology*. 69-70.
10. Gopale O, Jethwa S, G. A review of medicated lozenges. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Development*. 130-140.
11. Pravalika, J., Venkata Usha Sri, J., Asritha, J., Aravindh, B., & Sekhar, C. H. Review article on lozenges. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, 2026; 13(1).
12. Matthews D, Adegoke O, Shephard A. "Bactericidal activity of hexylresorcinol lozenges against oropharyngeal organisms associated with acute sore throat." *BMC Research Notes*. 2020; 13: 99. Supports antimicrobial activity and sore throat relief provided by medicated lozenges.
13. Sanjay K Chakraborty. HALITOSIS AND MOUTHWASHES. *Med J Armed Forces India*. 1998 Jul; 54(3)
14. Sujata Tungare, Nowera Zafar, Arti G, Halitosis, National Library of medicine.
15. G.S. Madhushankar, Yamunadevi .A, Haltosis, An Overview Part 1st
16. Cleveland Clinic. Health articles are based on evidence-backed information and reviewed by medical professionals to ensure accuracy, reliability and up-to-date clinical standards.
17. Kokate CK, Purohit AP, Gokhale SB. *Pharmacognosy*. 5th ed. Pune: Nirali Prakashan; 2014; 14.83.
18. Kokate CK, Purohit AP, Gokhale SB. *Pharmacognosy*. 5th ed. Pune: Nirali Prakashan; 2014; 14.126-14.129.
19. Kokate CK, Purohit AP, Gokhale SB. *Pharmacognosy*. 5th ed. Pune: Nirali Prakashan; 2014; 8.6-8.7.
20. kokate c.k. P'cognogy, Treage & Evang, *Pharmacognosy wHo monographs on Selected medicinal Plants, Indian Pharmacopeeia*.
21. Hawal Dar RM, Yenare N. Herbal Lozenges. *International Open Access, Peer Reviewed and Referred Journal*. 177-182.
22. Porwal U, Sharma N. Review on Lozenges in Pharmaceutical Field Globally. *Indian Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology*. 67-74.
23. Batheja P, Thakur R, Michniak B. Basic biopharmaceutics of buccal and sublingual absorption. In: Touitou E, Barry BW, editors. *Enhancement in Drug Delivery*. London, New York: CRC Press, Taylor and Francis Group; 2006; 189.
24. Remington. *The Science and Practice of Pharmacy*. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams and Wilkins; dosage forms including lozenges (troches), their formulation, advantages and

mechanism of action.

25. Das PC. Textbook of Medicine. 3rd ed. Calcutta: Current Books International; 1991; 232-237.

HERBAL LOZENGES FOR HALITOSIS

NATURAL BREATH FRESHENER & THROAT SOOTHING

100%
NATURAL
ACTIVES

Sr. No.	Ingredients	Quantity	Role
1	Peppermint Extract	2.4 ml	Breath Freshner
2	Clove Extract	1.2 ml	Antibacterial
3	Liquorice Extract	1.6 ml	Soothes Throat
4	Ginger Extract	1.2 ml	Antimicrobial
5	Menthol	0.4 gm	Cooling Sensation
6	Isomalt	36 gm	Base Sweetening
7	Citric Acid	0.8 ml	Taste enhancer
8	Gum Acacia	4.2 gm	Natural binder
9	Purified Water	Q.S	Solvent
10	Sodium Benzoate	0.16 gm	preservative

BENEFITS

- ✓ Helps reduce bad breath (Halitosis)
- ✓ Provides long-lasting freshness
- ✓ Soothes throat irritation
- ✓ Supports oral hygiene

DIRECTIONS FOR USE:

Allow one lozenge to dissolve slowly in the mouth.
Do not chew or swallow whole.

STORAGE:

Store in a cool and dry place away from direct sunlight.

Marketed By :

Abasaheb Kakade
College of B Pharmacy,
Bodhegaon

Manufactured By :

Aarti Kapre and
Dhanraj Kharad

	MFG DATE	18 MAY 2026
	EXPIRY DATE	17 JUNE 2026
	MRP (Inclusive of All Taxes)	₹ 50 /-

BEST BEFORE THE DATE OF EXPIRY

KEEP IN A COOL
& DRY PLACE